

AN INTRODUCTORY GUIDE TO THE MAIN CONCEPTS OF MARKETING

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Abstract. This article explains fundamental phenomena in the sphere of marketing and types of marketing strategies are described defining each sub-direction. Moreover, it analyzes the procedure and positive results of a good marketing strategy. Marketing is the set of activities a company undertakes to support the purchase and sale of its products or services. It includes advertising, selling, and delivering goods to consumers or businesses.

Key words. marketing, the 4 Ps of marketing, types of marketing strategies, traditional marketing, digital marketing, electronic marketing, outdoor marketing, and print marketing.

Introduction

Marketing is concerned with activities undertaken by a company to support the purchase and sale of a product or service. Marketing is the means by which goods are advertised, sold, and delivered to consumers or businesses. Some marketing is carried out on behalf of a company by affiliates. the American Marketing Association gives the following official definition, approved in 2017, for marketing: "*Marketing is the activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large.*"(1)

Professionals in a company's marketing and promotion departments use advertising to capture the attention of important potential consumers. Promotions are aimed at certain demographics and may include celebrity endorsements, unique phrases or slogans, noteworthy packaging or graphic designs, and total media exposure.

As a discipline, marketing encompasses all the activities a business does to attract and retain clients. Writing thank-you notes, going to golf with possible customers, promptly responding to calls and emails, and getting together for coffee or dinner with clients are all examples of networking with former or future clients who are part of the profession. At its most basic level, marketing seeks to match a company's products and services to customers who want access to those products. Matching products to customers ultimately ensures profitability.

Main part

Product, price, place, and promotion are the Four Ps of marketing. The Four Ps collectively make up the essential mix a company needs to market a product or service. Neil Borden popularized the idea of the marketing mix and the concept of the Four Ps in the 1950s.

Product. A "product" is an item or goods that a firm intends to sell to clients. The product should aim to fill a gap in the market or satisfy customer demand for more of an item that is currently on hand. Marketers must comprehend the product being offered, how it differs from its rivals if it can be combined with another product or product line, and whether there are any alternatives on the market before they can create a suitable campaign.

Price. A price is the price at which a company will sell a product. When determining a price, a company must take into account several factors, such as unit cost price, marketing costs, distribution expenses, and competing products in the market. Is the proposed price point good enough for consumers?

Place. Place refers to where the product will be sold. A key factor to consider is whether the company will be selling the product in a physical store, online, or both. If the product is sold in a store, what type of physical product placement will the product receive? If it is sold online, what type of digital product placement will it receive?

Promotion. The fourth P is promotion. This is the most important part of the overall marketing communications strategy. There are many different types of promotion, including advertising, sales promotion, public relations promotion, direct marketing promotion, sponsorship promotion, and guerilla marketing. The type of promotion varies depending on the stage of the life cycle of the product. Marketers know that consumers associate the price and distribution of a product with the quality of the product, and they factor this into their overall marketing strategy.

Types of Marketing Strategies

Marketing encompasses a vast array of strategies that are both extensive and diverse. As the industry progresses, it is important to acknowledge that certain strategies may be more suitable for specific companies than others.

Traditional Marketing Strategies. Before technology and the internet, traditional marketing was the primary way companies would market their goods to customers. The main types of traditional marketing strategies include:

Outdoor Marketing: This entails public displays of advertising external to a consumer's house. This includes billboards, printed advertisements on benches, sticker wraps on vehicles, or advertisements on public transit.

Print Marketing: This entails small, easily printed content that is easy to replicate. Traditionally, companies often mass-produced printed materials, as the printed content was the same for all customers. Today, more flexibility in printing processes means that materials can be differentiated.

Direct Marketing: This entails specific content delivered to potential customers. Some print marketing content could be mailed. Otherwise, direct marketing mediums could include coupons, vouchers for free goods, or pamphlets.

Electronic Marketing: This entails the use of TV and radio for advertising. Through short bursts of digital content, a company can convey information to a customer through visual or auditory media that may grab a viewer's attention better than the printed form above.

Event Marketing: This entails attempting to gather potential customers at a specific location for the opportunity to speak with them about products or demonstrate products. This includes conferences, trade shows, seminars, roadshows, or private events.

Digital Marketing. The marketing industry has been forever changed with the introduction of digital marketing. From the early days of pop-up ads to targeted placements based on viewing history, there are now innovative ways companies can reach customers through digital marketing.

Search Engine Marketing: This entails companies attempting to increase search traffic through two ways. First, companies can pay search engines for placement on result pages. Second, companies can emphasize search engine optimization (SEO) techniques to organically place high on search results.

E-mail Marketing: This entails companies obtaining customer or potential customer e-mail addresses and distributing messages or newsletters. These messages can include coupons, discount opportunities, or advance notice of upcoming sales.

Social Media Marketing: This entails building an online presence on specific social media platforms. Like search engine marketing, companies can place paid advertisements to bypass algorithms and obtain a higher chance of being seen by viewers. Otherwise, a company

can attempt to organically grow by posting content, interacting with followers, or uploading media like photos and videos.

Affiliate Marketing: This entails using third-party advertising to drive customer interest. Often, an affiliate that will get a commission from a sale will do affiliate marketing as the third party is incentivized to drive a sale for a good that is not their original product.

Content Marketing: This entails creating content, whether eBooks, infographics, video seminars, or other downloadable content. The goal is to create a product (often free) to share information about a product, obtain customer information, and encourage customers to continue with the company beyond the content.

Result and Discussion

Effective marketing strategies can provide numerous advantages to a company. Developing the optimal strategy and effectively implementing it may present certain obstacles; nevertheless, when executed skillfully, marketing can generate the following outcomes:

- Audience Generation. Marketing enables a company to effectively reach out to individuals who are likely to find value in its product or service. In some cases, these individuals are already aware of their needs, while in other cases, they may not even realize it yet. By employing marketing strategies, a company can successfully engage with a specific group of people who align with the target demographic it aims to cater to.

- Inward Education. Marketing plays a crucial role in gathering valuable information that can be internally analyzed to achieve success, for instance, market research that reveals a specific product is predominantly bought by women between the ages of 18 and 34. By acquiring such data, a company can enhance its understanding of this particular demographic, boost sales, and optimize resource allocation for greater efficiency.

- Outward Education. Marketing serves as a means to convey to the global audience the nature of your company, the range of products you offer, and the positive impact your company can have on people's lives. Through informative campaigns, marketing enlightens external stakeholders about the necessity of your product. Furthermore, marketing campaigns provide an opportunity for a company to introduce itself, its background, its proprietors, and the driving force behind its existence.

- Brand Creation. Marketing enables a company to adopt an assertive strategy in establishing its brand. Rather than relying solely on customer interactions to form their perception of the company, the company can proactively engage customers through targeted content or media to elicit desired emotions or reactions. This empowers the company to shape its identity even before customers have any direct experience with its products.

- Long-lasting. Marketing campaigns that are executed effectively can leave a lasting impression on customers. Since its introduction in 1965, the Pillsbury mascot has played a pivotal role in establishing a warm and friendly brand image that has endured over time.

- Financial Performance. The primary objective and advantage of marketing is to stimulate sales. Strengthened, clearly defined, and favorable customer relationships increase the likelihood of sales engagement. By implementing effective marketing strategies, customers are inclined to choose your company, giving you a competitive edge over your rivals. Even if the products are identical, marketing has the power to establish that competitive advantage, influencing clients to select your brand over others.

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